

**MODERN TRENDS IN THE FORMATION OF MATHEMATICAL IDEAS
IN UZBEKISTAN AND FOREIGN COUNTRIES**

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Purpose of the Paper. Scientific and methodological support of future pedagogues, their professional training are among the main issues in improving the process of teaching children of preschool age. In particular, the development of mathematical imagination and knowledge in children has a special place in their growth as intellectually mature people. Mathematical knowledge is given to children in a clear system and sequence, taking into account what they have learned and what they can do. Children's successful mastery of mathematical concepts is directly related to the development of their perception, that is, their sensory feelings. The question of modern educational technologies, didactic games, methods and tools that are suitable for use in this process is covered in detail in this thesis. The purpose of the research is to deeply study and analyze the modern trends in the formation of mathematical concepts in Uzbekistan and foreign countries.

Research Methodology. The main tasks of educating children is to prepare children for regular education based on national and universal values, taking into account their innate abilities, interests, needs and opportunities for physical, mental and spiritual development. The ability to generalize and abstract grows on the basis of determining the characteristics of objects and comparing these objects to each other and dividing them into groups based on these characteristics. Therefore, until the child goes to school, in order to form mathematical concepts in preschool educational organizations, all educational activities are carried out in an integrated manner. In today's age of rapid development of science and technology, we must

pay serious attention to the acquisition of necessary and necessary knowledge from preschool age so that children can easily learn experiences in various fields and use them in practice. In particular, mathematical knowledge is of great importance in the life of a child, in his all-round development. How clear and solid the first mathematical concepts are, ensures the strength of children's thinking, their processes of analysis and synthesis, logical thinking, and drawing conclusions. The subject of educational activities, goals and tasks, expected results, necessary equipment, progress of educational activities are written in full. During the educational activities, the topics are explained to the children in a simple way and reinforced with the help of practical work and various interactive games. At the end of each educational activity, questions are asked to determine and strengthen children's knowledge. During educational activities, children learn new mathematical concepts and strengthen their knowledge and skills by completing independent practical tasks, solving tasks using various interactive methods, playing games and creating.

Results: Conclusion. If a child learns novelty in problem solving, an interesting method of problem solving, giving up the traditional methods he has always used, new solutions to the problem, understanding the essence of the main connection of the problem and finding different ways to solve it, solving practical problems, getting out of problems, if he has the ability to tell, then mathematical concepts are developed. Mathematical knowledge should be given to children in a certain system and consistency, while the new knowledge should be in a smaller amount, that is, at a level that children can master. That's why one task is divided into several small parts, and they are studied one after another.

Recommendations. Effective results are achieved if the first mathematical concepts are taught in an interesting and age-appropriate manner. As a result of such activities, children learn to agree with a team, to support each other, to help each other, to behave in a team along with learning general knowledge, and they have self-confidence, such qualities as independent thinking and the ability to

express one's thoughts beautifully are formed. The goals of mathematics are general educational, practical and educational goals. Practical goals include children's ability to relate theory to practice, their knowledge of sets and numbers; It includes having a basic idea about the ratio of sizes (amounts) to each other, the simplest geometric figures, knowing place and time. should develop the skills to be able to apply to solve related questions and issues.

Implications. Exercises on grouping objects and geometric shapes by various signs are of great importance, at the same time, such exercises strengthen children's knowledge of shape, size, quantity, etc. In order to strengthen knowledge, the educator uses exercises of various nature, i.e. exercises related to practical, game, competition elements, interactive methods. Game elements are especially widely used in the education of three-four-year-old children. It is important to remember that changing the didactic material and method is a tool that ensures the acquisition of knowledge and skills without special stress. You should not get too attached to the game moments, because the game can distract from the main thing - mathematical work, as a result, children will not be able to master the knowledge and skills provided for in the training plan.

The work related to mathematics should teach children to be more disciplined, diligent, thorough, accurate, able to control their thoughts and conclusions, especially to pay attention to the fluency of their thoughts based on observation, experience and understanding. Children develop interest in mathematical knowledge, the ability to solve mathematical problems with patience and diligence. Mathematical education greatly contributes to the development of the basic skills of inductive and deductive thinking, mental operations, that is, the ability to analyze, synthesize, compare, abstract and generalize, to develop perception and intelligence, spatial imagination and imagination.

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Umar Khayyam, Nasriddin Tusi, Jamshid Ghiyasiddin al-Koshi, Ulugbek and many other great ancestors of ours made a great contribution to the development of arithmetic in their works, and remain the national pride of our people. . Their names and great contributions to the development of world civilization are now known to the whole world. We will get acquainted with their works. Muhammad ibn Musa Khorezmi was born in 783 in Khiva, Khorezm. He was interested in science from a young age. He diligently studied Arabic, Persian, Indian and Greek languages. Known as a sage, he was invited to Baghdad, which was considered a great scientific and cultural center of his time, at the beginning of the 9th century. Having created a blessing in the Khorezm palace, he actively participated in the first academy of the East ("Bayt ul-Hikmat") "House of the Wise". Although Khorezmi created many works, not all of them have reached us. Khorezmi's works on arithmetic and algebra opened a new era in the history of mathematics, the period of medieval mathematics, and made an incomparable contribution to the development of mathematics in the following centuries. Students often heard the words algebra and algorithm. Algebra is a large branch of mathematics, and algorithm is the main term of modern calculation techniques and mathematics. The words algebra and algorithm are associated with the name of the mathematician, astronomer and geographer, Al-Khorazmi, the father of modern algebra.

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